

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC DEMOCRACY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10485188>

The socio-political changes and reforms implemented in our society are causing citizens to become active.

Necessary political-legal, socio-economic and scientific-educational bases for establishing New Uzbekistan have been created in our country. Also, to review the current mechanisms of law-making and parliamentary control from the point of view of effectiveness, to increase the initiative of the public in state management by ensuring the participation of citizens in these processes, to connect deputies with their voters and senators with citizens in the regions within the framework of "Electronic Parliament" Issues such as proper communication, discussion of the problems of voters and digitization of the decision-making process have been identified as priorities for the next five years.¹

Participation of citizens in socio-political processes is usually indicated as a vital aspect of democracy. In the following years, in order to deepen the democratic reforms and strengthen the role of political parties in the modernization of the country, the issue of introducing a mixed (majoritarian-proportional) system of elections to representative bodies has been defined as a priority for the state and society, and it is appropriate to carry out these processes through the development of today's electronic democracy.²

As a result of e-democracy, citizens can express their opinion and influence the decision-making process in their community, region, country or globally. E-democracy can be achieved not only through old technologies such as television and radio, but also through new technologies such as the Internet, mobile phones, and electronic voting systems. These new technologies are

¹<https://lex.uz/docs/> (Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026")

²<https://lex.uz/docs/> (Decree No. PF-158 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 "On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030")

widely used participatory tools. A large number of stakeholders can access data and input directly through the internet. Large groups will also be able to provide real-time input at public meetings through electronic survey tools (networks and platforms).

Advantages of e-democracy

- more members of the public can be involved in expressing their views on the website, by e-mail or through other electronic means of communication to influence planning and decision-making;
- increases the number and types of persons who use their democratic rights through feedback sent to decision-making bodies on various proposals and issues;
- creates a virtual public space where citizens can interact, discuss problems and exchange ideas;
- allows citizens to participate in discussion processes at their convenience;
- it will be possible to reach a very large audience with convenience and low cost;
- facilitates interactive communication;
- distributes large amounts of data quickly, efficiently and non-destructively.

Existing problems:

- may exclude non-online participation;
- results can be manipulated, so the results of online surveys should be carefully considered;
- requires a lot of time and effort to synthesize and understand a large amount of input;
- autoresponder list servers should be avoided, email lists with many active subscribers generate so much information that they can confuse people.

Principles of successful planning:

- to create a detailed website that provides information about the project to be submitted for discussion and to ensure awareness of the information entered;
- keep the site well organized and updated;
- using standard HTML format to make the site as inclusive as possible;
- provide details of subscription/unsubscribe procedures;
- set up your online communication through the website;

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-counting the number of people who visit the site provides useful information about how many people are concerned and what issues the community is interested in.

According to the "Electoral Democracy Index"³ conducted by the "V-Dem Institute" ⁴at the University of Gothenburg, Sweden in 2023, Denmark, Sweden, Norway, Switzerland, Estonia, New Zealand, Belgium, Iceland, Costa Rica, Finland, Australia, Germany, France, After countries such as the Netherlands, Luxembourg, Spain, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Italy, Great Britain (0.84) took the 20th place, while Uzbekistan (0.22) took the 142nd place in this indicator. The number of countries included in this list is 179.

TABLE 3. COUNTRY SCORES FOR THE LIBERAL DEMOCRACY INDEX (LDI) AND ALL COMPONENTS INDICES, 2022

⬆ Indicates that the country's score has improved over the past 10 years, substantively and at a statistically significant level
 ⬇ Indicates that the country's score has decreased over the past 10 years, substantively and at a statistically significant level
 SD+/- reports the standard deviation to indicate the level of uncertainty

COUNTRY	LIBERAL DEMOCRACY INDEX (LDI)			ELECTORAL DEMOCRACY INDEX (EDI)			LIBERAL COMPONENT INDEX (LCI)			EGALITARIAN COMPONENT INDEX (ECI)			PARTICIPATORY COMPONENT INDEX (PCI)			DELIBERATIVE COMPONENT INDEX (DCI)		
	RANK	SCORE	SD+/-	RANK	SCORE	SD+/-	RANK	SCORE	SD+/-	RANK	SCORE	SD+/-	RANK	SCORE	SD+/-	RANK	SCORE	SD+/-
Denmark	1	0.89	0.04	1	0.92	0.036	2	0.98	0.012	2	0.97	0.024	5	0.71	0.018	5	0.97	0.637
Sweden	2	0.87	0.042	3	0.9	0.038	1	0.98	0.011	13	0.9	0.044	27	0.65	0.026	23	0.9	0.626
Norway	3	0.86	0.045	4	0.9	0.041	4	0.97	0.018	1	0.97	0.024	28	0.65	0.018	1	0.99	0.64
Switzerland	4	0.85	0.044	2	0.9	0.038	8	0.96	0.025	6	0.93	0.04	1	0.88	0.02	2	0.98	0.645
Estonia	5	0.85	0.045	5	0.89	0.04	6	0.96	0.021	17	0.89	0.053	38	0.63	0.037	48	0.83	0.634
New Zealand	6	0.83	0.046	8	0.89	0.039	11	0.95	0.025	19	0.88	0.056	6	0.71	0.04	33	0.88	0.63
Belgium	7	0.83	0.046	6	0.89	0.041	14	0.93	0.031	5	0.93	0.038	30	0.65	0.025	17	0.92	0.636
Ireland	8	0.82	0.048	7	0.89	0.04	15	0.93	0.033	18	0.89	0.052	26	0.65	0.039	18	0.92	0.637
Costa Rica	9	0.82	0.047	12	0.87	0.042	9	0.96	0.023	20	0.88	0.054	14	0.67	0.033	7	0.96	0.634
Finland	10	0.82	0.05	13	0.86	0.046	5	0.96	0.023	11	0.91	0.043	25	0.65	0.02	10	0.93	0.634
Australia	11	0.81	0.048	14	0.86	0.045	3	0.97	0.019	31	0.84	0.061	18	0.66	0.044	13	0.93	0.635
Germany	12	0.81	0.047	15	0.86	0.043	7	0.96	0.021	4	0.94	0.038	15	0.66	0.012	3	0.98	0.629
France	13	0.8	0.05	10	0.88	0.043	18	0.92	0.033	26	0.85	0.061	40	0.63	0.038	11	0.93	0.637
Netherlands	14	0.8	0.049	17	0.85	0.045	10	0.96	0.023	14	0.9	0.046	48	0.61	0.04	6	0.96	0.639
Luxembourg	15	0.79	0.05	9	0.88	0.042	26	0.91	0.04	3	0.95	0.039	58	0.59	0.066	4	0.97	0.637
Spain	16	0.79	0.048	11	0.87	0.039	24	0.91	0.041	40	0.8	0.069	29	0.65	0.032	30	0.88	0.629
Czech Republic	17	0.79	0.049	16	0.86	0.043	16	0.93	0.031	12	0.91	0.05	57	0.59	0.047	35	0.87	0.63
Slovakia	18	0.78	0.051	20	0.85	0.048	17	0.93	0.03	39	0.81	0.066	17	0.66	0.046	92	0.66	0.626
Italy	19	0.77	0.05	21	0.85	0.045	19	0.92	0.033	7	0.93	0.041	4	0.76	0.033	15	0.92	0.64
United Kingdom	20	0.77	0.051	22	0.84	0.047	21	0.92	0.032	34	0.83	0.069	20	0.66	0.028	39	0.87	0.631
Chile	21	0.76	0.051	30	0.81	0.049	12	0.95	0.022	60	0.72	0.076	24	0.65	0.04	8	0.96	0.638
Hungary	22	0.76	0.051	18	0.85	0.045	31	0.89	0.04	27	0.85	0.06	42	0.62	0.04	31	0.88	0.63
USA	23	0.74	0.055	27	0.82	0.051	22	0.92	0.035	74	0.66	0.086	19	0.66	0.015	36	0.87	0.634
Canada	24	0.74	0.056	19	0.85	0.047	38	0.87	0.048	51	0.76	0.075	22	0.65	0.024	50	0.83	0.63
Latvia	25	0.74	0.057	26	0.82	0.052	28	0.9	0.043	30	0.84	0.062	16	0.66	0.043	46	0.84	0.629
Lithuania	26	0.73	0.057	35	0.79	0.055	13	0.95	0.025	22	0.86	0.055	7	0.7	0.043	55	0.8	0.624
Japan	27	0.73	0.052	23	0.83	0.046	35	0.88	0.044	8	0.93	0.044	75	0.56	0.052	22	0.9	0.63
Guinea	131	0.1	0.021	148	0.19	0.019	130	0.27	0.071	142	0.39	0.084	94	0.34	0.064	155	0.22	0.634
Eswatini	152	0.1	0.02	171	0.12	0.015	137	0.32	0.073	174	0.19	0.074	152	0.26	0.097	168	0.11	0.646
UAE	153	0.09	0.016	172	0.1	0.018	147	0.3	0.059	117	0.5	0.083	175	0.09	0.058	144	0.29	0.634
Qatar	154	0.08	0.017	174	0.09	0.016	146	0.3	0.063	146	0.36	0.051	177	0.07	0.043	137	0.39	0.625
Uzbekistan	155	0.08	0.015	142	0.22	0.023	158	0.2	0.046	131	0.45	0.089	170	0.13	0.057	129	0.47	0.621
Palestine/Gaza	156	0.08	0.017	166	0.14	0.017	153	0.26	0.062	103	0.57	0.096	131	0.41	0.087	154	0.22	0.645
Burundi	157	0.08	0.017	149	0.19	0.018	156	0.21	0.058	155	0.31	0.09	156	0.24	0.097	157	0.21	0.641
Sudan	158	0.07	0.016	158	0.17	0.018	157	0.21	0.056	156	0.31	0.092	153	0.26	0.076	162	0.17	0.654
Russia	159	0.07	0.014	145	0.21	0.022	160	0.17	0.043	133	0.44	0.092	130	0.41	0.06	158	0.18	0.636
Cambodia	160	0.06	0.014	146	0.21	0.02	165	0.15	0.045	167	0.25	0.08	140	0.33	0.06	164	0.16	0.625
Venezuela	161	0.06	0.013	143	0.21	0.02	167	0.14	0.042	158	0.28	0.082	117	0.46	0.065	176	0.06	0.639
Azerbaijan	162	0.06	0.012	150	0.19	0.017	163	0.16	0.039	160	0.28	0.074	168	0.14	0.049	169	0.1	0.639
South Sudan	163	0.06	0.016	168	0.13	0.012	159	0.18	0.058	177	0.1	0.051	164	0.15	0.057	171	0.1	0.636
Cuba	164	0.06	0.013	152	0.18	0.016	166	0.14	0.045	55	0.75	0.075	154	0.26	0.076	147	0.28	0.629
Bahrain	165	0.06	0.013	170	0.12	0.017	162	0.17	0.049	143	0.39	0.068	173	0.1	0.052	156	0.21	0.631
Equatorial Guinea	166	0.05	0.012	157	0.17	0.013	170	0.13	0.043	150	0.34	0.083	171	0.12	0.051	170	0.1	0.639
Tajikistan	167	0.05	0.011	155	0.18	0.014	171	0.12	0.04	173	0.19	0.066	169	0.13	0.046	165	0.14	0.625
Myanmar	168	0.05	0.014	173	0.09	0.011	164	0.16	0.054	169	0.24	0.079	139	0.33	0.062	153	0.22	0.641
Yemen	169	0.04	0.013	169	0.12	0.015	169	0.13	0.047	178	0.06	0.039	158	0.22	0.056	175	0.07	0.637
Saudi Arabia	170	0.04	0.012	179	0.02	0.007	161	0.17	0.049	137	0.43	0.069	174	0.1	0.057	152	0.25	0.638
Belarus	171	0.04	0.01	156	0.18	0.016	173	0.09	0.033	57	0.74	0.083	162	0.15	0.054	173	0.08	0.637
China	172	0.04	0.01	177	0.08	0.005	168	0.14	0.04	152	0.33	0.083	163	0.15	0.055	146	0.28	0.632
Turkmenistan	173	0.04	0.01	163	0.15	0.009	175	0.08	0.035	164	0.27	0.073	176	0.07	0.034	177	0.04	0.649
Nicaragua	174	0.03	0.008	153	0.18	0.015	177	0.06	0.028	170	0.23	0.082	137	0.35	0.059	178	0.04	0.643
Syria	175	0.03	0.01	165	0.14	0.006	174	0.08	0.037	175	0.16	0.059	165	0.15	0.056	172	0.09	0.637
Chad	176	0.03	0.008	164	0.14	0.017	176	0.07	0.029	172	0.21	0.071	146	0.28	0.067	143	0.33	0.621
Afghanistan	177	0.03	0.012	176	0.08	0.008	172	0.09	0.045	179	0.05	0.036	178	0.05	0.04	174	0.08	0.649
Eritrea	178	0.01	0.005	178	0.07	0.005	178	0.03	0.018	127	0.47	0.1	179	0.03	0.027	167	0.11	0.63
North Korea	179	0.01	0.005	175	0.09	0.01	179	0.02	0.019	154	0.31	0.078	166	0.15	0.033	179	0.02	0.643

In determining the above indicators, "freedom of wide opinions" - i.e. freedom given to the media and mass media, freedom of men and women, "share of the population with the right to vote", "freedom of organizations" - parties,

³ Varieties of Democracy (V-Dem) produces the largest global dataset of over 31 million democracies for 202 countries from 1789 to 2022. Nearly 4,000 scientists and other national experts measure hundreds of different attributes of V-Dem. V-Dem provides new ways of studying the nature, causes and effects..

⁴ https://v-dem.net/documents/30/V-dem_democracyreport2023_highres.pdf

opposition parties, "exact electronic indicator" - freedom of election, was determined by such indicators as the possibility of purchasing electronic votes.

FIGURE A2.2. THE V-DEM ELECTORAL DEMOCRACY INDEX (EDI)

Criteria for determining electoral democracy

Citizens' use of social media evokes a range of emotions, from friendship or support to disagreement and aggression. Their behavior and the type of influence of social networks can be predicted to some extent depending on the type of social networks, as well as the segment of users. Social media affects different populations to different degrees. They show the presence of influence in the following areas:

- marketing, tourism, environment, health, mental health and emotions, vaccination issues, politics and government, IT, crisis and disaster management, organizations and businesses.

Information technology and social media have changed business as a whole, and the new model of online engagement has had a powerful impact on the decision-making process of CEOs and managers.

The influence of social networks on all aspects of society's life is increasing and deepening with their development. Social media has come a long way from platforms where children and youth play games to professional job search networks. Along the way, their influence grew and deepened, especially in the field of entrepreneurship. Influencing the way people think can also distort the decision-making process. The concern is that this effect continues to increase, and it can be both positive and negative for the employees or the business. Using social networks, the enterprise has the opportunity to positively influence its consumers and develop communication with them. However, the influence of social media on senior management must be properly managed. Professionals involved in the decision-making process should be aware of this influence, and manage it properly in the formation of opinions and attitudes, as well as in their

professional activities. More in-depth research on how social media can negatively impact decision makers is needed, as such research is lacking.⁵

Another key indicator of e-democracy today is e-government. "Electronic government" means an information structure that is being created to change the methods of solving tasks faced by state bodies. Initially, public sectors used information technology for internal use in individual departments and organizations, but now information technology has a great value and operates based on the principles of "fast, good, cheap, accessible".

By introducing ICT for the population in the activities of state bodies, new opportunities for public administration will be created. The first of two important functions of e-government is the relationship between government and society; the second strengthens internal relations between state organizations of different levels (central, regional, local) and agencies in different fields (legislative, executive, judicial).

The Unified Interactive State Services Portal (my.gov.uz) plays an important role in the development of the electronic government system. In particular, as of October 2023, 82.9 million applications were received through the portal. The number of registered users of the single portal reached 5.1 million. Today, 505 state services are provided through the Single portal.⁶

In conclusion, the widespread introduction of electronic democracy in society will make it easier for citizens to carry out their activities in socio-political, economic or other vitally important issues, reforms in society will be implemented based on public opinion, and various corruption cases will be limited. It also saves time and money in relations between the state, society and citizens.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026"
2. Decree No. PF-158 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 "On the strategy of Uzbekistan - 2030"
3. https://v-dem.net/documents/30/V-dem_democracyreport2023_highres.pdf

⁵ THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESS /- Srđana Taboroši, Aleksandra Kovačević, Biljana Maljugić University of Novi Sad, Technical faculty "Mihajlo Pupin", Zrenjanin, Serbia (06.2022)

⁶ [https://my.gov.uz/uz/site/statistic-page\(08.10.2023 y\)](https://my.gov.uz/uz/site/statistic-page(08.10.2023 y))

4. THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN THE DECISION-MAKING PROCESS /-
Srđana Taboroši, Aleksandra Kovačević, Biljana Maljugić University of Novi Sad,
Technical faculty "Mihajlo Pupin", Zrenjanin, Serbia (06.2022)
5. <https://my.gov.uz/uz/site/statistic-page>(08.10.2023 y

